

from which results all expected frequencies n'_i (see table) using the next recurrent formula

$$n'_i = \frac{k+i-1}{i} \times R \times n'_{i-1}$$

where k , p , and q are parameters of the negative binomial $(q-p)^k$, m_x is the mean of data from the n unit samples ($n = 330 \text{ m}^2$), P_0 is probability of the first expected frequencies of n'_0 and n'_i and n'_{i-1} are any two successive expected frequencies with indices of $i-1$ and i .

Observed frequencies n_i were similar to the expected values n'_i that could have been obtained if all egg masses were distributed according to negative binomial distribution (see table). The corresponding χ^2 (3.9), gave too great a risk α (0.691) of being wrong when rejecting the null hypothesis.

The observed data must therefore be contagiously aggregated. Considering the holistic behavior of the insect, that they are not social insects, and that observed egg mass numbers are too small, such a grouping of data does not result from

females forming a group on a given night to lay eggs (see figure) and is not frequently done at random. It also could not result from accumulated eggs laid night after night in the same place by a few females.

Females can lay more than one egg mass a night, and all of these masses are located very close to one another. Different groups of egg masses resulted from the same number of individual females (see figure). Other experiments in different areas of Côte d'Ivoire supported these results. ■

Integrated pest management—other pests

Feeding behavior of parakeets on rice in Hill Region of Karnataka, India

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Roseringed parakeet *Psittacula krameri* Scopoli and blossom-headed parakeet *Psittacula cyanocephala* Linn. are the two main bird species that feed on rice in the Hill Region of Karnataka.

We studied damage done by parakeets to 4 ha of rice at Mudigere (13.0° 7' N and 75.0° 37' E) during Nov-Dec 1990. We used binoculars to observe the birds. We saw birds alighting on trees bordering ricefields at 0640 h. Most perched on tree branches or fence wires. At about 0720 h, three or four birds started to ricefeed in the fields. At about 0730, foraging groups of up to 20 birds of both species flew into the fields.

Individuals hovered by rice plants, cut, and then picked panicles. Each bird picked six to eight panicles during a period of 5-30 min, returned to its site, fed on the grains, and then flew back to the fields.

From 1000 to 1500 h, parakeets sought cover in trees adjacent to the ricefields. After 1500 h, five to six birds resumed feeding, which continued until

about 1745 h. Birds then returned to their roosting sites.

Foraging activity was interspersed by preening, beak cleaning, and resting. Individuals and groups spread over a wide area in a field but stayed within sight of each other. In 95% of the situations, the 55 flocks observed congregated only at field borders.

Foraging range of feeding flocks was 3-4 km and feeding range, 1.5-2.0 km. Flock size varied from 50 to 113 birds/ha ($n = 55$). Rice feeding lasted up to 24 d. Parakeets depredated stacked panicles soon after harvest. Birds preferred harvested panicles to panicles on the standing crop because they could feed conveniently on grains without hovering.

Panicle loss was computed as parakeets/ha $\times$ panicles/parakeet/day $\times$ feeding days. Panicle loss was converted to grain weight by counting and weighing all grains/panicle from a random sample of 100 panicles on eight different observation days.

Total yield loss was categorized as depredative loss (grain consumed) and extra-depredative loss (grain spilled). Mean depredatory loss of 71.4% differed significantly ($P = 0.05$) from the mean extra-depredative loss of 14.2% ($n = 8$).

Farmers lost 0.3 t/ha to parakeets. Considering that average harvest in Mudigere is 2.5 t/ha, yield loss caused by parakeets is economically important. Rice crops from milk grain stage to harvesting need to be protected from parakeets. ■

Effect of selected genera of plant parasitic nematodes on germination of rice seeds in eastern India

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Rice in eastern India is seeded shortly after the premonsoon showers. In this situation, nematodes attack emerging seedlings and cause mortality.

We recorded seed germination in soils inoculated with nematodes to study their potentiality (Table 1). Results showed that only *H. mucronata* reduced seed viability significantly. We found that nematodes penetrated the seeds, affecting the embryos or inhibiting the emergence

Table 1. Effect of selected genera of plant parasitic nematodes on germination of Jaya seeds in eastern India.

Treatment	Germination (%)	Reduction (%)
Uninoculated	96.0	—
<i>Meloidogyne</i> (100 2d-stage juveniles)	94.5	1.5 (6.8) ^a
<i>Hoplolaimus</i> (100)	90.5	5.5 (12.9)
<i>Pratylenchus</i> (100)	90.0	6.0 (14.2)
<i>Hirschmanniella</i> (100)	81.5	14.5 (22.4)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate angular value = 15.3 at LSD (0.05).

of coleoptiles and plumules. Reduced viability due to nematode pathogens was due to mechanical injury and penetration of pathogens into root tissues, which caused rapid mortality in germinating

Table 2. Frequency distribution of selected genera of plant parasitic nematodes on rice in eastern India.

Type and no. of samples collected	<i>Meloidogyne</i>		<i>Hoplolaimus</i>		<i>Pratylenchus</i>		<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	
	Frequency	$\bar{x}^a$	Frequency	$\bar{x}$	Frequency	$\bar{x}$	Frequency	$\bar{x}$
<i>Upland rice - year one</i>								
Soil 61	18	221	16	42	22	94	20	68
Root 54	33	303	20	39	19	148	33	172
<i>Upland rice - year two</i>								
Soil 43	33	304	36	69	25	87	30	120
Root 38	30	408	30	111	24	263	25	20
<i>Rainfed lowland rice - year one</i>								
Soil 35	13	118	14	86	18	49	30	116
Root 42	21	279	11	195	7	198	32	479
<i>Rainfed lowland rice - year two</i>								
Soil 44	14	33	9	114	8	82	28	332
Root 44	29	212	27	373	26	388	20	622

^a $\bar{x}$ = larval and adult population/100 g soil or 1 g fresh weight of root tissue.

seedlings. We found that *Pratylenchus* and *M. graminicola* accounted for 7-18% of the nematode infestation of rice roots by the 4th day after infestation (DAI) and up to 40% by the 7th DAI.

Frequency of parasitic nematodes in the rhizosphere of upland rice in order of prevalence were genera *Meloidogyne*, *Pratylenchus*, *Hirschmanniella*, and *Hoplolaimus*; in rainfed lowland rice, *Hirschmanniella*, *Pratylenchus*, *Meloidogyne*, and *Hoplolaimus* (Table 2). ■

Farming systems

Effect of preceding crops on rice yield

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Rice was planted on about 2 million ha in the Punjab State, India, in 1991-92. Rice usually follows nonrice crops. We evaluated the yield and yield attributes of rice grown after crops of wheat, winter maize, field pea - green gram, Swede rape - green gram, potato - transplanted winter maize, Indian rape - transplanted Swede rape - green gram, potato - sunflower, and Indian rape - sunflower

from 1988 to 1992 in fixed plots laid out in randomized block design. Intensity of the crop rotations ranged from 200 to 400%.

Soil of the experimental field was calcareous, sandy loam with pH 8.1 and 0.28% organic C. All crops received the recommended fertilizer package and practices except sunflower after potato, which was grown without applied fertilizers.

Mean grain yield of rice following wheat was lowest at 4.8 t/ha. Maximum rice yield of 6.5 t/ha was obtained in potato - transplanted winter maize - rice sequence, although it was at par with rice yield from Swede rape - green gram - rice and potato - sunflower - rice systems.

These cropping systems produced significantly higher rice yield, effective tillers, panicle lengths, and test weights than the other systems (see table).

Winter maize - rice, field pea - green gram - rice, Indian rape - transplanted Swede rape - green gram - rice, and Indian rape - sunflower - rice systems all produced about 5.2 t rice/ha.

Farmers can obtain higher rice productivity by selecting suitable preceding cropping systems, such as potato - transplanted winter maize, Swede rape - green gram, and potato - sunflower. These systems can also help improve soil fertility and contribute to crop diversification. ■

Effect of preceding crops on yield attributes and grain yield of rice. Punjab, India, 1988-92.

Preceding crops	Grain yield (t/ha)					Effective tillers/plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	200-grain weight (g)
	1988-89	1989-90	1990-91	1991-92	Mean			
Wheat	5.0	5.9	5.6	3.4	4.8	8.5	22.4	5.25
Winter maize	5.4	6.2	5.7	3.7	5.2	8.6	23.0	5.25
Field pea - green gram	5.6	6.0	5.2	3.9	5.2	8.1	22.8	5.25
Swede rape - green gram	6.6	7.1	6.6	5.2	6.2	9.5	23.7	5.50
Potato - transplanted winter maize	6.8	7.4	6.6	5.9	6.5	9.6	23.7	5.75
Indian rape - transplanted Swede rape - green gram	4.0	6.9	5.4	4.8	5.2	8.8	22.2	5.50
Potato - sunflower	6.5	7.0	6.3	6.0	6.2	9.6	23.9	6.00
Indian rape - sunflower	3.7	7.0	5.5	4.7	5.2	8.2	22.7	5.25
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.3	0.8	0.9	0.6	0.8	1.2	0.60